

HISTORY OF THE FORMATION, ARCHITECTURAL ASPECTS AND REPAIR OF THE SHIRBUDUN PALACE OF BUKHARA

USMONOV ERKIN TOYIROVICH

assistant

Bukhara engineering-technological institute
(Uzbekistan)

erkin.usmonov.arx@mail.ru

XUDAYQULOV MEHRIDIN MARDANOVICH

assistant

Bukhara engineering-technological institute
(Uzbekistan)

mehridin.xudoyqulov@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7690300>

Abstract: This article discusses the history of architecture and recovery of the Shirbudun Palace in Bukhara and the role and ethnography of this sacred historical monument.

Key words: Palace, architecture, monument, urban planning, shosh, pool, mosque, repair, restoration.

HISTORY OF THE PALACE

Shirbudun palace — One of the political bases of the Emirs of Bukhara. The palace began during the period 1870 during the time of Amir Muzaffarkhan (1860-1885) ruled by the Bukhara Emirate. In the 1870s, Letrizgar (wooden master) was built in the Shiruzul (wooden master) master Rahim Hayotov, others, such as palaces, shops, pools, mosques. In the appearance of the palace, signs of the architecture of Iran and European countries are felt [1]. The palace mainly met the messengers, fairs and various fences. The Shirbudong Palace is distinguished by European furniture, chandeliers. In about 3 verst from Registan (1 verst - 1,066 km 1,066 km) in the Ole Olafsen memorities [3]. Amir Muzaffarkhan held these palaces, bids, and weddings, weddings and various events, except meters and influential guests. In the palace, construction continued construction in the region during the reign of Amir Muzaffarkhan. In particular, the palace built many palace rooms and luxury halls during the period of Amir Abdullahadkhan [2].

Amir Muzaffarkhan held these palaces, bids, and weddings, weddings and various events, except meters and influential guests. During the festivets, the Palace of Shirwudung raised 500 tents at the Palace of Shirbudun. This event was a unique fair in the city of Bukhara. During the reign of the rulers after Amir Muzaffarkhan in the palace, construction work continued in this area. In particular, Amir Abdulahadkhan built a luxurious hall and many palace rooms in the building [2]. This building, which left a great impression on visitors to Bukhara, was at the disposal of the Agricultural Inspectorate of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic in 1920-1924. This palace was completely destroyed. A new garden was built around it. In the 1960s, the water management building of Bukhara region was built in the park. During the years of independence, this building in the park was given to the community of citizens of the neighborhood, and it is still operating today. The Shirbudin complex, which was built by the Bukhara emirs at great expense, gained social, economic, political and cultural importance in its time [5].

INFORMATION ABOUT THE PALACE FROM LOCAL SOURCES

There is information about the palace in the books of local historians Mirza Abdulazim Sami, Mirza Salimbek, Muhammad Ali Baljuvani and Sadriddin Aini, and brief information about the building is given. Devanbeg Mirza Salimbek, who worked in high positions in the palace of Bukhara Emirate, writes that every six months when he went from Tashkent to Bukhara, he met with Amir Muzaffarkhan at Shirbudin Charbog. Palace historian Mirza Abdulazim Sami says in his work: "The powerful emir (meaning Amir Abdulahad Khan) replaced his famous father on the throne of the Bukhara Emirate in 1303 (1885-1886) and, like his ancestors, has been ruling on the carpet of citizenship and rule for about ten years. He spends most of his time in Bukhara, ark, Shirbudin and Sitorai Mohi Khosa" he wrote. Muhamad Ali Baljuvani spoke about the Mangit rulers: "The rulers came with their subjects to rest in the palace. There are many special places in Karshi, Shakhrisabz, and Bukhara districts. All kinds of castles were built and there are castles in other places[4]," he wrote. In his memoirs, Sadriddin Ainiy said: "The main playground in Shibadandan was located on both sides of the main road that passes in front of Amir Charbog. On the way out of the city, there was a walled area on the left side, it was called chil tanobi (ten hectares), it has a big gate. In this enclosed square, there were jame mosque, chavki (general party grounds) and theaters, butchers and kitchens occupied other parts of the square. From the end of this square there was a gate to the main road, on the south side of this place there was a gatehouse road of the Amir's garden and a porch on the side of the garden gate, where the people watched" [5], he writes.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE PALACE IN TRAVELERS' MEMOIRS

The Shibusun palace is also mentioned in the diaries and memories of foreign tourists, such as Dmitri-Kavkazki (1849-1916), the academician of the Russian Academy of Artists (1849-1916), the great British officer Ole Olufsen (1865-1929), and the Russian photographer Sergei Mikhailovich Prokudin-Gorsky (1863-1944), who visited Bukhara Emirate. information is found. Photographer Dmitry-Kavkazkiy, who visited Bukhara Emirate on February 20, 1888, describes the Shirbudin Palace in his diary as follows: "There is also a room in the palace that looks like a train carriage in which the emir went to Russia to be crowned, and it leaves an interesting impression on the person who enters it. The tour of the palace was an unforgettable day for me. "Unfortunately, I didn't have time to go around the palace completely and I couldn't draw a picture" [4], he wrote. The book of Olufsen (1865-1929), who traveled in the Bukhara Emirate in the 1890s, contains information about architectural objects in the Bukhara Emirate, and information about the Shirbudun Palace was given. In his reminiscences about the palace: "Shirbudin Palace is located in the western part of the road from Old Bukhara to New Bukhara. In the eastern part there is a stable and a servant's residence" [3], he writes. Russian photographer Sergei Mikhailovich Prokudin-Gorsky (1863-1944), who was in Bukhara in 1907-1911, managed to take the first color photographs. In particular, he photographs the portrait of Amir Olimkhan, scenes depicting the state of the people, the front and back of the Shirbudun palace, the throne palace, and gardens.

Shirbudun - from Shirbadan, pronounced like Sherbudin, these words are different from each other. For example, the word Shirbadan in the Persian-Tajik language means Shir - milk, badan - body, while the word Shirbudun means the people of the Shir. One of the ancient Turkic nations was named after Shir, Sir, Chir. Sir budun - "mystery people", "mystery people" is found in the monument of Kultegin (732) [11]. So, the word budun preserved in the name of Shirbudun village, located east of Bukhara, indicates that this toponym belongs to the period when this word was used (i.e. X-XI centuries), and that there was a shir (sir, chir) belonging to

Turkic peoples living in one place of Bukhara at that time. Because in many cases, the people who lived in this village were called by the name of clan (people, people). Nowadays, the word Shirbudun is mainly pronounced as Sherbudin because of the presence of the Sherbudin shopping complex. In 2007, the neighborhood assembly of citizens of this area was given the name of Shirbudun [5].

The role of the Shirbudun Palace of Shirbudun in Bukhara

ARCHITECTURE

The walls of the palace are 10 meters high and consist of a circular mud wall. Like other palaces, it has flat roofs and is surrounded by all kinds of fruit trees, flowers and rose bushes and beautiful gardens. Some of the palace buildings are made of brick, and some of them are made of wood [3].

Shirbudun Palace consisted of several small rooms decorated in Arab-Persian style. Some rooms are decorated with murals. The paintings in the medallions in the rooms combine the East and the West. There is also a room with a mirror in the palace, the height of the mirror is 4 arsh (1 arsh is equal to 0.711 meters), and the walls of the room are surrounded by frameless glass. The room is covered with a French carpet, and a French bronze chandelier hangs from the ceiling. The central dome of the room is decorated with Arabic-style decorations and has golden water. In the center of the palace courtyard there is a pool and a fountain made of white stone (marble)[10]. The palace houses the Emir's reception hall, richly decorated and furnished, with balconies and wooden pillars. The throne of the emir is located on the pulpit, the throne was a gift from the Russian emperor. The floors are covered with luxurious carpets. After the reception hall, there are columns and a marble staircase at the back, which overlooks the courtyard. The palace has various decorations, wooden pillars, verandas and beautiful balconies. It also features a main women's harem, vaulted rooms, baths, fountains, and lavish subtropical gardens around the inner courtyard [3].

References:

- 1.Rempel L.I. "Far and near". Tashkent: Literature and Art Publishing House named after Gafur Gulyam, 1981 — 304 pgs.
- 2.Sayfullayeva R, Mengliyev. "Modern Uzbek literary language". Tashkent: Science and technology, 2010 — 200 pgs.
- 3.Абдирашидов З. "Annotated bibliography of Turkestan materials in the newspaper Tarjuman," Токио, 2011 — 232 pgs.

HISTORICAL SOURCES

- 4.Мирза Салимбек. "History Salimi (Source on the history of the Emirate of Bukhara)". Translation from Persian Н. К. Норкулова. Tashkent: academy, 2009 — 330 pgs.
- 5.Муҳаммад Али Балжувоний. "The history is useless". Authors of translation, introduction and comments from Тажик Ш. Воҳидов, З. Чориев. Tashkent: academy, 2001 — 122 pgs.

